

EFFECTS OF FIBRE LENGTH AND LOADING ON ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE REINFORCED WITH VIRGIN OR RECOVERED CARBON FIBRES

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SUMMARY: The need for the recycling of polymeric composite materials has become an important requirement to guarantee their continued use and future growth. A fluidised bed process was used to recover carbon fibres from scrap epoxy prepreg. The fluffy recovered fibre was converted into a two dimensional veil using a papermaking process. The feasibility of developing an electromagnetic interference shielding material using the recovered fibre veil is presented in this paper. The effects of fibre length and loading on shielding performance were investigated using a similar grade of virgin carbon fibre. Overall, carbon fibre with length shorter than 14.4mm is preferable as good veil uniformity is easily attained to achieve a better shielding performance. The average shielding value of the recovered fibre veil was 12% lower than the 14.4mm long virgin fibre veil. An average shielding value of 41dB has been achieved using a layer of 80gsm recovered fibre veil.

KEYWORDS: EMI shielding, composite recycling, fluidised bed, fibre length, fibre loading, carbon fibre veil

INTRODUCTION

The advantages of fibre reinforced thermoset composites such as design flexibility and integrity, light weight, chemical resistance and improvement in mechanical properties have found their application increasingly in industries such as aerospace, automotive, marine, wind energy and electronic equipment. However, concerning recycling, the existing technologies and infrastructures for the composite waste are weak and 98% of the wastes are land-filled and incinerated [1]. As a result of recent implementation of EU Directives, the need for the recycling of composite materials has emerged as an important requirement to guarantee continued use and future growth.

Mechanical grinding is a conventional recycling approach for thermoset composite. Ground recyclates are normally used in BMC and SMC industries as a filler particularly for weight saving in applications where the requirement for mechanical properties is not so critical [2-3]. Pyrolysis is another recycling approach, which combusts scrap composite in an inert atmosphere at elevated temperature. Most of the organic matter decomposes into gases and are condensed into liquid form in the later stages. Solid residues consist of the inorganic fractions of filler, reinforcement fibres and carbonaceous substances like char and coke. Subsequent ashing or oxidation in air is necessary to burn off all the carbonaceous substances to obtain clean fibres and fillers [4-5]. Recently, chemical recycling for thermoset composites has drawn considerably attention, which involves a chemical solvent to dissolve the themorset

matrix to separate out the reinforcement fibre. For examples, glass fibre was recovered from uncured phenolic resin using methanol [6] and nitric acid was employed to recover carbon fibre from cured epoxy resin [7]. At the University of Nottingham, a fluidised bed process has been developed. This is an innovative recycling process that is able to recover clean carbon fibre from contaminated or mixed thermoset composite scraps [8-9]. The objective of this work was to investigate the feasibility of applying the recovered carbon fibres for the development of electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding materials.

A limitation in the use of electrically insulating polymers for electrical and electronic equipment is their transparency to electromagnetic radiation and this has inhibited electromagnetic compliance. Electromagnetic compliance is a key requirement to ensure proper functionality of all electronic components in a common electromagnetic environment. Enhancing the electrical conductivity of a polymer improves its EMI shielding ability and three approaches may be used: conductive coatings, intrinsically conductive polymers (e.g. polyaniline, polycetylene and polyrrole) or incorporation of conductive filler or fibres (e.g. graphite, copper or aluminium). In the present work, only the final method is addressed. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of fibre length and loading on EMI shielding of polyester composite reinforced with either virgin or recovered carbon fibre.

FLUIDISED BED RECYCLING PROCESS

Fig. 1 shows a schematic representation of the fluidised bed recycling process. Fluidising air, preheated to 450-550°C, is fed to a bed of silica sand, with particle diameter ranging from 0.35 to 0.85mm, with a fluidising velocity of 0.8 to 1.0m/s. Scrap composite material is fed into the bubbling fluidised bed and at high temperature the thermoset resin rapidly decomposes releasing fibres into the air stream. The fibres are separated from the air in a cyclone and collected for recycling. The exhaust air is directed to an afterburner to oxidise all of the polymer products at 1000°C before being released to atmosphere. An initial optimisation of the fluidised bed recycling process parameters, such as fluidising velocity, fluidising temperature and sand particle diameter, had been undertaken to improve the property of the carbon fibre recovered from epoxy composite [10].

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

The experimental investigations involved the manufacture of glass reinforced composite plaques in which a surfacing veil made from carbon fibre was used to provide electromagnetic shielding. The performance of recovered carbon fibre was compared with virgin carbon fibre.

Virgin carbon fibre

Epoxy sized Toray T600SC-24000-60E virgin carbon fibre was supplied by The Advanced Composites Group. The fibre diameter is 7µm and the density is 1.8g/m³. A pneumatic chopper gun was used to cut the fibre into 5 different lengths, i.e. 6.4, 9.6, 14.4, 19.2 and 28.8mm respectively.

Fig. 1: A schematic representation of fluidised bed recycling process

Recovered carbon fibre

Scrap prepreg, MTM28-2 epoxy resin reinforced with the same grade of virgin unidirectional carbon fibre, provided by The Advanced Composites Group, was cured at 100°C for 5 hours. The cured prepreg was cut using a paper guillotine into ribbons with fibre length of 30mm. A Retsch SM2000 miller with a 20mm by 20mm square aperture sieve was used to shred the prepreg into irregular small strips. The shredded prepreps were then processed in the fluidised bed. The bed temperature was set to 550°C with an air velocity of 1.0m/s. The average silica sand diameter was 0.85mm.

Fabrication of carbon fibre veil

Both virgin and recovered carbon fibres were converted separately into a two dimensional, randomly oriented veil using a wet papermaking process. The water solution comprised 4.5g/l of Hydroxyethyl cellulose binding agent from Dow Chemical, 0.6g/l of Merpol® OJ non-ionic surfactant from Sigma-Aldrich and 0.3g/l of Bevaloid 6686W anti-foaming agent from Rhodia. Weighed samples of carbon fibre were added into the water solution and stirred using a high-shear impeller at a speed of 800rpm for 2-11mins. The process was undertaken using a baffled tank to ensure better dispersion efficiency. The fibre was then filtered out onto a stainless steel mesh and dried in an oven at 100°C for 15mins. The areal density of the veil was ranging from 20 to 100gsm with an increment of 20gsm. The thickness of the veil was then measured using a micrometer at 6 random locations.

Fabrication of the composite

Polyester resin was chosen as the matrix material. It was supplied by Scott Bader and the type was Crystic 701PA. Composite specimens were moulded using a resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique with an injection pressure of 7 bars at room temperature. The RTM tooling was heated up to 60°C after resin impregnation. Before the RTM process, a preform was made to facilitate the placement of the carbon fibre veil and continuous glass filament mats (CFM), from Vetrotex, in the RTM tooling. It comprised a piece of carbon fibre veil on the top surface followed with 3 layers of 450gsm CFMs (U750/450/m2-6%binder), a layer of 375gsm CFM (U751/375/m2) and a layer of 450gsm CFMs (U750/450/m2-6%binder). The CFMs were used to build up the thickness of composite to about 2.8mm. The preform was pressed and consolidated at 70°C under a pressure of 30bar for 10 minutes.

EMI shielding effectiveness test

The EMI shielding effectiveness was measured according to a coaxial transmission line method based on ASTM D4935-99 standard [11]. A HP8752A network analyser with an input power of 5dBm was used to generate a plane-wave, far-field electromagnetic wave with a frequency ranging from 30MHz to 1.5GHz. The composite specimen was clamped in the nickel-coated brass specimen holder as specified by the standard. The transmitted wave was directed back to the network analyser via a coaxial cable. Three load samples and a reference sample were tested for each carbon fibre formulation. The average shielding effectiveness of the three load samples is reported in this paper.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of fibre loadings

A typical glass fibre reinforced polyester composite (GRPC) has an electrical conductivity between 10^{-10} and 10^{-12} S/m [12]. Such a low conductivity means the GRPC has little or no EMI shielding ability as shielding performance is directly proportional to the material conductivity. This agreed with the experimental result shown in Fig. 2a with SE values close to zero.

According to percolation theory, an electrically conductive network is formed when the incorporated volume fraction of carbon fibre is higher than the percolation threshold [13]. Below the percolation threshold, the composite behaves as an insulator or a semiconductor. In the present work, the dispersed fibres were filtered out by slowly draining the water solution through a stainless steel mesh to form a veil. The fibres were deposited on the mesh in a two-dimensional manner to form a conductive network and the veil thickness increased linearly with increasing fibre loading. The Pike and Seager percolation model [14] was used to calculate the percolation threshold for a two-dimensional “sticks” system with a random lattice configuration. The model was modified for the present work with the threshold expressed as the minimum veil areal density, N , at which a network of infinite size first becomes conductive. The value of N was estimated using Eqn. 1, where L was the carbon fibre length, ρ was the density of the carbon fibre and V was the volume of the fibre. Eqn.1 was used with assumptions that the fibre was straight, fully dispersed into single filaments and uniformly distributed across the veil. The result is tabulated in Table. 1. It can be seen that the percolation threshold decreases with increasing fibre aspect ratio. The 6.4mm long fibre requires the heaviest veil density to form a conductive network, i.e. 0.062gsm. The lightest veil density in the present work was 20gsm, which was much higher than the heaviest calculated percolation threshold. Hence, the EMI shielding ability of the GRPC specimen would be enhanced by incorporating a layer of electrically conducting carbon fibre veil.

$$\text{Minimum veil areal density, } N = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{4.236}{L} \right)^2 (\rho V) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2a: Shielding effectiveness of GRPC composite incorporated with a layer of 14.4mm long virgin fibre veil with different fibre loadings (from 20 to 100gsm) across the entire frequency span

Fig. 2b: Average shielding effectiveness of GRPC composite incorporated with a layer of 14.4mm long fibre veil with different fibre loadings

Carbon fibre length (mm)	Aspect ratio	Minimum veil areal density, N , (gsm)
6.4	914	0.062
9.6	1371	0.041
14.4	2057	0.027
19.2	2742	0.021
28.8	4114	0.014

Table 1: The minimum veil areal density with different fibre length at which a conducting network of infinite size is first formed

Fig. 2a shows the shielding results across the entire frequency span obtained from GRPC specimens incorporated with a layer of 14.4mm long virgin carbon fibre veils at various loadings. The shielding performance increases with increasing fibre loading. Similar trends were obtained from veils of other fibre lengths. The average shielding effectiveness across the frequency range from 30MHz to 1.5GHz at various fibre loadings is shown in Fig. 2b. Electromagnetic waves are attenuated by a shield in three different ways: reflection loss, absorption loss and multiple internal reflections [15]. Multiple internal reflections can be neglected if the absorption loss is greater than 9dB [16]. Reflection loss occurs when the wave passes through two different media. The degree of reflection is related to the difference in characteristic impedance between them. Each veil has a fibre loading well above the electrical conductivity percolation threshold and hence the resistivity should be about the same. Veil thickness increased with increasing fibre loading and the thickness of the veil is an important factor in absorption loss. The amplitude of an electromagnetic wave decreases exponentially when passing through a conductive medium due to ohmic losses by induced currents in the medium [17]. With the absorption loss mechanism, the shielding effectiveness could be further increased with increasing fibre loading.

Effect of fibre lengths

During the veil making process, it was found that the difficulty of fibre dispersion increased with increasing fibre length. For example, the 6.4mm fibre took only 2 minutes to be fully dispersed without any fibre entanglement. However, when the virgin fibre length was above 14.4mm, curvy and undispersed fibre bundles persisted in the solution and the number of fibre bundles increased with increasing fibre loading. Prolonging the dispersion time did not solve the problem. The reason for the bundles was apparently the presence of long fibre lengths, which increased the tendency for mechanical interlocking between fibres.

Fibre length is also an important factor in the fluidised bed recycling process. In the experiment, approximately 90% by weight of the fibre was recovered and the rest agglomerated in the sand bed forming dense fibre platelets, which were contaminated with sand particles. A preliminary model was suggested to understand the mechanism of fibre agglomeration [18]. The model was based on percolation theory to study the effect of fibre length, bed temperature, fluidising velocity and feed rate on the onset of agglomeration. It was identified that the shorter the fibre length, the higher the feed rate that could be tolerated before the advent of fibre agglomeration.

Fig. 3 displays the effect of virgin carbon fibre length on the shielding performance. On the one hand, at short fibre lengths (between 6.4 and 14.4mm), it indicates that the shielding performance is not significantly affected by the fibre length. On the other hand, the 19.6 and 28.8mm long fibres show a lower shielding value. Generally, composite conductivity or shielding effectiveness increases with increasing aspect ratio of fibrous reinforcement [19-20]. However, when the fibre volume fraction is well above the percolation threshold, the influence of fibre length on the composite conductivity is less significant [21]. As already described, the minimum veil areal density in this investigation was much higher than the estimated percolation threshold. This would explain why fibre lengths between 6.4mm and 14.4mm do not affect shielding effectiveness. The reduction in shielding effectiveness with long fibres, i.e. 19.6mm and 28.8mm, might result from a reduction in fibre dispersion with increasing fibre length. The less dense areas might act as a discontinuity [17] and degrade the shielding value.

Fig. 3: Average shielding effectiveness of GRPC composite incorporated with a layer of virgin fibre veil with different fibre lengths

Recovered carbon fibre

Carbon fibre recovered from the fluidised bed process is fluffy and with some degree of agglomeration due to the spiral motion within the cyclone. The weight average length was measured using an image analysis method [9]. 780 fibres were measured and the weight average length was 16.4mm. The fibre length distribution is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 5a shows the improvement in shielding effectiveness in GRPC specimen attained by incorporation of layers of recovered carbon veil. A comparison in shielding performance between 14.4mm long virgin fibre veil and recovered fibre veil is shown in Fig. 5b. The 14.4mm virgin veil is chosen as its fibre length is the closest to the weight average length of the recovered fibre. At 20gsm, the shielding performance of recovered fibre veil was 13.4% lower than the virgin veil. The reduction reached 17.3% at 100gsm. On average, it was about 12% lower than the 14mm long virgin fibre. Unlike the virgin fibre, the shielding performance decreased when the areal density was higher than 80gsm.

As shielding performance is affected by the electrical conductivity of carbon fibres, a four-point probe single fibre resistivity measurement was set up to investigate if the conductivity of the recovered fibre was affected by heat treatment during fluidised bed recycling process. It was found that the conductivity of single recovered fibres was only 0.5% lower than a virgin fibre. As a result, the conductivity could not be a dominant factor in accounting for the overall 12% reduction in shielding performance of the recovered fibre veil. The decrease in shielding performance might result from a reduction in fibre dispersion in the veil making process due to the presence of long recovered fibres and the slight degree of fibre agglomeration. Undispersed fibre bundles persisted in the solution causing poor uniformity across the fibre veil and the difficulty in fibre dispersion increased with increasing fibre loadings.

Fig. 4: Length distribution of recovered carbon fibre

Work is currently ongoing to quantify the veil uniformity in order to assess its likely effect on shielding effectiveness. In order to solve this problem, a bigger dispersion tank may be used to keep the relative fibre concentration low in the solution even at higher fibre loadings. Nevertheless, in the present work, a layer of 80gsm recovered veil gave an average EMI

attenuation of 41dB, which should be adequate to meet FCC Class B requirement for commercial EMI shielding applications as reported by Colaneri and Shacklette [23].

Fig. 5a: Shielding effectiveness of GRPC composite incorporated with a layer of recovered fibre veil with different fibre loadings (from 20 to 100gsm) across the entire frequency span

Fig. 5b: Average shielding effectiveness of GRPC composite incorporated with a layer of recovered fibre veil or 14.4mm virgin fibre veil with different fibre loadings

CONCLUSIONS

By incorporating a single layer of virgin carbon fibre veil on the surface of a fibre reinforced polymer composite, its shielding performance was enhanced with increasing fibre loading. In the case of short virgin fibre lengths (6.4 to 14.4mm), as long as good fibre dispersion is achieved in the veil making process, the shielding performance was found to be independent of the fibre length. A lower shielding value was observed for longer carbon fibres (19.6 and 28.8mm) and this might result from non-uniformities in the veil areal density acting as a shield discontinuity.

The feasibility of developing an EMI shielding using recovered carbon fibre has been studied. Compared to a veil made from virgin fibre of a similar mean fibre length, the recovered fibre veil has a shielding performance that is 12% lower. This is understood to be due to non-uniformities in the recovered fibre veil. Nevertheless an 80gsm veil made from recovered fibre can achieve an average EMI attenuation of 41dB.

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